

THE EMPHASIS ON HUMAN RIGHTS IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS HARMONIZATION WITH INTERNATIONAL LAW REQUESTS

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Annotation: Article the reforms carried out by the Foundation, the role of human rights in its dignity, the rights of women and the opportunities given to the younger generation today have been cited.

Keywords: Human Rights, co-ordination, conference, strategy, collective character, citizenship.

Introduction: as a person comes into the world, human freedoms also arise with him. As a person grows up, his life needs at the same time increase in his right, responsibility. Human rights are the characteristics of a person's vital need for survival, maturation, his connection with society, the state and other persons. The system of human rights and freedoms has its own stages of development.

Material and methods: the article analyzes the ongoing reforms on human rights and legal meanings, the legitimate interests of human and citizens, women's rights, gender equality, in the case of a goal, which uses a comparative analysis method. Reforms to strengthen human rights serve as the main criterion in the construction of the state and society.

Results and considerations: many literature mention the three-generation stage of human rights and include the following stages.

The first stage is considered the first generation of human rights – civil and political law.

The second generation of human rights is formed under the influence of a number of objective and subjective factors. At the end of the 19th century in the early 20th century, there were significant shifts in the economy in most industrialized countries.

The third generation of human rights has a superior and collective character to the so-called "rights of solidarity" States. According to the generally recognized rules, these rights include the right to peace, the right to an unparalleled natural environment, the right to use the economic and cultural heritage of human kind, etc.

Independence is remarkable for the fact that the greatest goal of Uzbekistan, which is boldly guided by Democratic paths, is aimed primarily at the implementation of reforms aimed at the interests of our people. These aspects are also enshrined in our Constitution. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, "democracy is based on universal human principles, according to which a person, his life, freedom, honor, dignity and other rights without exception are the highest values." This law is also enshrined in Article 13 of our Constitution. In accordance with the work carried out on ensuring human rights and freedoms in our country, the Republic of Uzbekistan is dedicated to the implementation of the rules of the decree on the "program of measures dedicated to the 60th anniversary of the adoption of

the Universal Declaration of human rights” of the head of State confirming that national institutions are trying to strengthen.

The activities aimed at improving the legislation in the field of human rights are to some extent dependent on the interaction of the representative with the members of the Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the deputies of the legislative chamber. The OECD and Omdusman movements focused on further strengthening cooperation. Cooperation with the Upper House of Parliament is aimed at improving the sphere of control activity in the field of compliance with human rights by conducting monitoring on the implementation of legislation in the field of human rights, participating in conferences seminars and other events, as well as exchanging information about the situation on compliance with human rights. When the concept of human rights reached the path of great independence of our mamalakat, our people began to fully exercise their rights. Within a short time, a legal sphere was established in which citizens provided rights and freedoms, the main people of democracy and civil society were formed, the practice of law enforcement was introduced. It is worth knowing that to date, in our Constitution, in addition to the constitutional and legal foundations and guarantees of the protection of human rights and freedoms, its organizational mechanisms have been created, the social, economic, political rights of citizens are expressed in the strategic directions of development of society, fair and democratic principles of management, as well as the foundations of our spiritual values. A clear example of this is the creation of various benefits for people with disabilities of the II group of our president and persons with disabilities , for example, funds are provided for their admission to studies on the basis of a state grant, for their preferential study and education. As an example, moral and material support is provided to children of a family who have lost their breadwinner, who need social protection.

Socio-political scandals are primarily associated with the political system in force in the state. This system serves to prevent violations of the system and freedoms of human rights. The issues of guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of Zero-citizens are inextricably linked with the social policy that the state is pursuing. According to Article 45 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan “the rights of minors, incapacitated and lonely elderly are under the protection of the state”¹ marked as. In addition, measures to ensure human rights in our country are paid great attention to the upbringing of human rights in the spirit of loyalty to the generally recognized ideas and values of human rights. Of particular importance is the state guarantee of the implementation of the rights and freedoms of people and citizens enshrined in the Constitution and laws.

In order to protect human rights in our country, the president of our state Sh. Mirziyoyev's farm on Human Rights “on approval of the national strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan’ with the essence of the content, the main directions of activity of state bodies and organizations responsible for the implementation of the norms of international human rights treaties were established.

One of the main directions is the identification , analysis ,elimination of the causes and conditions that prevent the implementation of the recommendations of the UN priority bodies for ison rights and contractual committees .

¹ O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi Toshkent 2019

The goal of the national strategy is to determine the main tasks and directions of implementation of the state policy, which is being consistently carried out in Uzbekistan to ensure human rights and freedoms.

Samarkand forum on Human Rights is also held every two years with the participation of experts and guests of Honor from foreign countries at the highest level and representatives of international organizations .

Within the framework of the national strategy, it is envisaged to achieve results in Qui by implementing the established tasks:

The effectiveness of the implementation of international human rights standards in legislation and law enforcement practices will increase and national legislation will be improved. The effectiveness of the implementation of recommendations in the field of human rights is increased.

An organizational and legal and other complex system of measures will be created aimed at ensuring reliable protection of human rights and freedoms, the effectiveness of international organizations in the implementation of recommendations in the field of human rights will be increased. A system of organizational legal and other comprehensive measures will be created aimed at ensuring reliable protection of human rights and freedoms, effective control of Parliament ,territorial representative bodies and the public over the necessary implementation of international obligations will be ensured ,increasing the legal literacy of the population in the field of human rights, further improving the activities of information dissemination ,education in this regard, By bringing cooperation with international and regional structures in the field of human rights to a new level, the country's indicators on international rankings and indices in the field of human rights and freedoms are improved.

I.A.Karimov had singled out in his speech to the VIII session of the Supreme Assembly of the II convocation that the provision of order ,legislation and harmony in the stability of the state was of great importance. Democratic instes protecting human rights with state bodies and law enforcement agencies also have a special role in this regard. As you know, according to the recommendations of the second UN General Conference on human rights, it is recommended that all countries of the world create a democratic system of human rights insts. In the following years, National instutites engaged in human rights issues were formed in our country, like many developed progressive countries in the world. Human rights commissions have been established in various countries.

Human rights include many branches. For example, women's law, which has now become a topic of relevance. Women and men are equal rights, which is also dictated by Article 46 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Women's rights are those that strengthen the socio-economic, civil and political status of women. They are designed to protect women from discrimination based on gender.²

Women's rights are one of the main human rights guaranteed in many international treaties, resolutions, declarations and action programs in the field of human rights. The main international treaty on women's rights is the United Nations Convention on the elimination of discrimination against women in all forms [CEDAW] and its Optional Protocol. In addition, women's rights are important elements of other UN treaties, including the Universal Declaration of human rights, the International Covenant on Civil and political rights, the

² Ozbekiston Respublikasi Fuqarolik huquqi ????????

International Covenant on economic, social and cultural rights, the convention on the elimination of racial discrimination and the Convention on the rights of the child, among others.

The respublikasi of Uzbekistan always pays special attention to the provision of women's rights. Uzbekistan was one of the first in Central Asia to ratify the UN Conventions on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women on May 6 , 1995, and other international documents.

Since Uzbekistan joined the UN Convention on the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women, six periodic reports have been submitted to the UN committee to end discrimination against women.

Thanks to consistent legislation and other measures aimed at protecting the rights, freedoms and interests of women, they are pursuing their rights and freedoms, knowledge and skills in entrepreneurship, education, health, science and socio – political spheres. There are many activities in our country to protect women. In particular; chapter 14 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is called "family" and is dedicated to the protection of family, motherhood and childhood. In order to prevent early marriage, Article 15 of the Code defines the age of marriage for men and women as 18 years.

Article 78 of the Labor Code does not allow pregnant women and women with children under three years of age to disproportionately vos from hiring due to their duly pregnant or having children;³ Section 84 does not set a preliminary test for the recruitment of pregnant women, women with Boles under the age of three , persons sent to work (women with children) in the most established jobs for the enterprise.

The family chest will have to pay alimony until the child reaches adulthood, including through the provision of immovable or movable property or other valuables. In 2017-2021, a number of architectural documents were adopted aimed at ensuring and protecting women's rights. In the field of raising women's roles in the political and social life of mamalakat ;

On September 2, 2019, the Republic of Uzbekistan law 'on equal rights and guarantees of opportunities for women and men' was adopted .

Under the leadership of the president of the Senate of the House of Commons, a commission was formed on issues of gender equality .

The activities of the committee on issues of women and gender equality in the Upper House of Parliament and the Commission on family and women's issues in the lower house were established. On June 25, 2019, the Electoral Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. It enshrines equal suffrage regardless of the gender, race, position, education, training nature of citizens. Regulates relations in the field of protection of women from violence. The law provides a broad definition of a number of concepts, such as sexual assault, physical abuse, economic violence, mental abuse, violence, harassment.

By the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 19, 2021 "on additional measures for the rehabilitation of women affected by the use of violence" PQ-5116, the Republican Center for the rehabilitation and adaptation of 1ta women, 14 regional centers and 14 na'munali inter-district centers, as well as 1146 short-numbered 'Call-centers' where victims of violence can apply

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Mehnat kodeksi b.

Another of the branches of human rights is the right of the child. The Charter of the peoples of the United Nations declared that they have the right to special care and assistance to children, taking into account the fact that they have confirmed their faith in the fundamental rights of Man, the honor and dignity of the human individual, and have made a covenant to promote social progress and improving living conditions. It is recognized that for the maturation of the child's personality in a healthy and comprehensively harmonious way, ensuring that the main organization of the society provides the necessary protective support in order to achieve the considered family and medical environment in which all its members, especially children, will be able to grow up and have well-being, take on. This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.

Conclusion: In conclusion, practical work is carried out in every field in order to protect the immunity of human rights in our country. In particular, in order to ensure the inviolability of human rights, the rights of anyone to receive knowledge, use of medical services for free, gender equality, parental responsibility for minors, the fact that lonely elderly are under state protection and the like are reflected in our consultation. The country President SH.M.Mirziyayev has concluded mutual friendship and cooperation agreements with a number of countries on the protection of human rights. Also, the president of the country met with the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights Folkler Turk on March 15 of this year. At the meeting, the UN High Commissioner highly appreciated Uzbekistan's achievements in ending child and forced labor, promoting gender equality, ensuring the independence of judicial offices. On the 75th anniversary of the Universal Declaration of human rights, the adoption of the National Education Program in the field of human rights, the ratification of the UN Convention on the rights of Persons With Disabilities, the preventive mechanism with the participation of civil society institutions for the Prevention of torture, as well as the return of women and children from conflict areas to their.

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